

Composite construction materials from plant resources: mechanical characterization and statistical approach

Hocine Khelifa^{1*}, Abderrezak Bezazi², Nasser Bouhemame³, Haithem boumediri², Gilberto Garcia Del pino⁴, Paulo N.b. Reis⁵, Fabrizio Scarpa⁶, Zied Driss⁷

¹ Department of Mechanics, University of Larbi Tébessi -Tébessa 12000, Algeria

² Laboratory of Applied Mechanics of New Materials (LMANM), University 8 May 1945, Guelma 240, Algeria

³ Department of Mechanics, University of Kasdi Merbah Ouergla 30000, Algeria

⁴ Department of Mechanical Engineering, State University of Amazonas, Manaus, AM, Brazil

⁵ University of Coimbra, CEMMPRE, Department of Mechanical Engineering, 3030-788 Coimbra, Portugal

⁶ Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, Queens Building, University Walk, BS8 1T

⁷ Laboratory of Electromechanical Systems (LASEM), National School of Engineers of Sfax, University of Sfax, Tunisia

Abstract: For ecological reasons, the recovery of agricultural waste has become a global necessity. These enormous residues, biodegradable, can be used with different percentages as a reinforcing element in cementitious matrices in building materials. This study deals with the influence of the length and percentage of date palm trunk fibers (DPTF) incorporated into bio-mortars. In order to improve the fiber/matrix cohesion energy, the extracted DPTFs underwent alkaline treatments, by varying the percentage of sodium hydroxide and the immersion time before being used in the preparation of bio-mortar. Compression tests were carried out to evaluation the mechanical properties, namely the ultimate stresses, Young's modulus and displacements. To do this, a design of experiment was carried out using the response surface methodology (RSM) in order to minimize the number of tests. The results obtained shows that the incorporation of DPTFs in the mortar can improve the mechanical behavior of the bio-mortar by 46.6% and 36.3% in the compressive strength and Young's modulus, respectively.

Keywords: bio-mortar; date palm trunk fiber (DPTF); compression tests; alkali treatment; response surface methodology

Graphical abstract

*Corresponding author: Hocine Khelifa
Email: khelifa_hocine@yahoo.fr